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ACUTE LEUKEMIA: MODERN DIAGNOSIS METHODS

Summary. The classification of acute leukemias, as well as modern views on their clinical picture, diagnosis and therapy are presented. Imagine the basic scheme of hematopoiesis. The stem cell is the parent pluripotent element of hematopoiesis; stem cells belong to the 1st undifferentiated class of cells. The exit of the stem cell into proliferation and differentiation, differentiation along the lines of lymphopoiesis or myelopoiesis is carried out by chance. 2nd class - partially differentiated cells, precursors of lympho-myelopoiesis, 3rd class - unipotent precursor cells.

Key words: tumor, hemoblastosis, leukemia, anemia, thrombocytopenia, complete blood count, bone marrow transplantation.

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ОСТРЫЙ ЛЕЙКОЗ: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ДИАГНОСТИКИ

Резюме. Представлена классификация острых лейкозов, а также современные взгляды на их клинику, диагностику и терапию. Представьте себе основную схему кроветворения. Стволовая клетка является исходным плюрипотентным элементом кроветворения; стволовые клетки относятся к 1-му недифференцированному классу клеток. Выход стволовой клетки на пролиферацию и дифференцировку, дифференцировку по линиям лимфопоэза или миелопоэза осуществляется случайно. 2-й класс - частично дифференцированные клетки, предшественники лимфوميелопоэза, 3-й класс - унипотентные клетки-предшественники.

Ключевые слова: опухоль, гемобластоз, лейкоз, анемия, тромбоцитопения, общий анализ крови, трансплантация костного мозга.

Leukemia is a clonal malignant (neoplastic) disease of the hematopoietic system. The incidence of leukemia is 150-200 cases per year per 1 million people, and there are 2 peak incidence: at 3-4 years and at 60-69 years, men get sick more often than women.

Depending on the forms of the cells that make up the tumor, acute and chronic leukemias are distinguished. Acute leukemia is represented mainly by blasts, while chronic leukemia is represented by mature and maturing forms.

Imagine the basic scheme of hematopoiesis. The stem cell is the parent pluripotent element of hematopoiesis; stem cells belong to the 1st undifferentiated class of cells. The exit of the stem cell into proliferation and differentiation, differentiation along the lines of lymphopoiesis or myelopoiesis is carried out by chance. 2nd class - partially differentiated cells, precursors of lympho-myelopoiesis, 3rd class - unipotent precursor cells. These 3 classes are morphologically unrecognizable. This is followed by 3 classes of morphologically recognizable cells: 4th class - blast cells (myeloblasts, lymphoblasts, erythroblasts, thromboblats), from which the 5th class is formed: maturing cells: promyelocytes, reticulocytes and from them - 6th class of mature blood cells. So, acute leukemias are a heterogeneous group of tumor diseases of the blood system - hemoblastoses. Acute leukemias are characterized by damage to the bone marrow by morphologically immature (originating from blast elements) hematopoietic cells. In the

future, or from the very beginning, infiltration by blast cells of various tissues and organs may occur. All acute leukemias are clonal; arise from 1 mutated hematopoietic cell.

Classification. In our country, the main forms of acute human leukemia were identified by I.A. Kassirsky, A.I. Vorobyov, Yu.I. Lorie, M.M. Degtyareva, F.E. Feinstein in the 1980s on the basis of the cytochemical features of the cytoplasm of blast cells, which make it possible to determine these forms and some of their morphological and clinical criteria. This classification was revised in 2000 by A.I. Vorobyov and M.D. A diamond to take into account all the signs of a tumor - morphological, immunophenotypic, karyological, clinical, etc.

According to this classification, acute leukemias are divided into:

1. Acute myeloid leukemias:

- acute myeloblastic leukemia, variant with $t(8;21)(q22;q22)$ and variant with rearrangements $11q23$;
- acute promyelocytic leukemia with $t(15;17)(q22;q11-12)$ and variants;
- acute myeloblastic leukemia, variant with $inv(16)(p13;q22)$ or $t(16;16)(p13;q22)$ and with pathological bone marrow eosinophilia, variant with rearrangements $11q23$;
- acute monoblastic leukemia, variant with $11q23$ rearrangements;
- acute erythromyelosis, acute erythromegakaryoblastic leukemia;
- acute monoblastic leukemia of newborns;
- acute megakaryoblastic leukemia;
- acute megakaryoblastic leukemia with myelofibrosis;
- acute myeloblastic leukemia with myelofibrosis;
- acute low percentage leukemia, variant with $5q$;
- secondary myeloid leukemias;
- acute macrophage leukemia.

2. Acute lymphoblastic leukemia:

- adult acute B-lymphoblastic leukemia, cytogenetic variants with:
 - $t(9;22)(q34;q11)$;
 - $t(1;19)(q23;p13)$;
 - $t(12;21)(p12;q22)$;
 - and with rearrangements $11q23$;

- immunophenotypic variants:
 - early pre-B (pro-B);
 - pre-B;
 - IN;
- acute B-lymphoblastic leukemia of children:
 - cytogenetic variants:
 - t(9;22)(q34;q11);
 - t(1;19)(q23;p13);
 - t(12;21)(p12;q22);
 - and with rearrangements 11q23;
 - immunophenotypic variants:
 - early pre-B (pro-B);
 - pre-B;
 - IN;
- acute plasmablastic leukemia;
- acute T-lymphoblastic leukemia of adults;
- acute T-lymphoblastic leukemia in children;
- acute T-lymphoblastic leukemia with aplastic syndrome;

3. Acute biphenotypic leukemias.

4. Acute undifferentiated leukemia.

Despite the fact that acute leukemias are named after the normal blasts of the corresponding hematopoietic lineages - lymphoblastic, myeloblastic, erythroblastic, monoblastic - tumor cells only to some extent correspond to their normal predecessors. In addition, some leukemias cannot be associated with any particular initial cellular element.

For example, acute promyelocytic leukemia is composed of cells with basophil, mast cell, and neutrophil traits. In addition, there are acute leukemias, the cells of which do not have signs of belonging to any hematopoietic lineage. Such leukemias are called undifferentiated.

The age of patients also leaves a certain imprint on the classification. As with other human tumors, childhood leukemias do not correspond to similar leukemias in adults or

the elderly in terms of treatment results. Such patients need other specific therapy programs.

Etiology. To date, many theories have been proposed for the occurrence of leukemia, but none has become dominant. Factors contributing to leading to the development of acute leukemia are:

- chromosomal abnormalities;
- exposure;
- toxic effects due to environmental pollution and drug therapy;
- previous diseases of hematopoiesis (myelodysplasia, refractory anemia, paroxysmal nocturnal hemoglobinuria, etc.).

Clinic. The onset of acute leukemia does not have a characteristic clinical picture: patients do not feel unhealthy until the widespread spread of tumor cells in the hematopoietic system and the development of organ disorders.

The main manifestations of acute leukemia:

- infectious diseases;
- intoxication syndrome;
- anemic syndrome;
- bleeding associated with thrombocytopenia;
- pain in bones and joints;
- enlarged lymph nodes;
- splenohepatomegaly.

All these signs can only be a reason to see a doctor, but in themselves they have no diagnostic value and are not early signs of tumor growth, although the patient often claims that before they appeared, he felt completely healthy. In any unclear or prolonged disease, it is necessary to conduct a blood test, in which obvious or indirect signs of acute leukemia can be detected.

The diagnosis of acute leukemia can only be established morphologically - by the detection of blast tumor cells in the blood or bone marrow.

Diagnostics. At the 1st stage of diagnosis, a general blood test is very useful. The manual count of blood cells used in many medical institutions in Russia has a number of

disadvantages (human factor and duration). Modern automatic analyzers eliminate these factors, making the results more reliable.

VAMP protocol

Preparation	Scheme of application
Vincristine	1.5 mg/m ² intravenously once a week from the 1st or 3rd day
Amethopterin (methotrexate)	20 mg/m ² once every 4 days intravenously
6- mercaptopurine	100 mg/m ² daily
Prednisolone	40 mg/m ² daily

There are 5 eight-day courses for the treatment of acute lymphoblastic leukemia.

VRP Protocol

Preparation	Scheme of application
Vincristine	2 mg/m ² intravenously once a week from the 1st or 3rd day
Rubomycin	80 mg/m ² per week
Prednisolone	40 mg/m ² daily

CAMP protocol

Preparation	Scheme of application
Cyclophosphane	120 mg / m ² / day
Amethopterin (methotrexate)	20 mg/m ² daily
6- mercaptopurine	60 mg/m ² daily
Prednisolone	40 mg/m ² daily

The hematological picture of acute leukemia can be presented in 2 versions:

- when blast cells enter the blood, young blast cells (80–90% of the leukocyte formula) and mature granulocytes, monocytes, and lymphocytes are found in it simultaneously; however, in a blood smear, the content of promyelocytes and myelocytes in acute leukemia is small and the “failure” in the formula between young and mature cells persists (leukemic failure);

- if blast cells have not yet acquired the ability to exit the bone marrow into the peripheral blood, but have already led to some disturbances, there are quite a lot of them in the bone marrow; in this case, as a rule, there will be disturbances in the composition of the cellular elements of the blood: leukopenia, anemia, thrombocytopenia or pancytopenia (aleukemic form of the disease).

At the 2nd stage of diagnosis, it is sufficient to carry out cytochemical marker reactions:

- positive reaction to sudan and peroxidase (acute myeloblastic leukemia);
- sharply positive reaction to nonspecific esterase (acute monoblastic leukemia);
- positive reaction to glycogen (acute lymphocytic leukemia).

When in doubt, a puncture study of the bone marrow is performed. It should be noted that when making a diagnosis of acute leukemia, it is necessary to differentiate its type in order to choose treatment tactics and prognosis of the disease.

Treatment. Modern methods of treatment of acute leukemia can guarantee remission in more than 80% of cases. Today they apply:

- polychemotherapy;
- glucocorticosteroids;
- immunotherapy;
- bone marrow transplantation;
- auxiliary methods: extracorporeal (leukapheresis, cytapapheresis), replacement therapy, syndromic and symptomatic therapy.

Principles of polychemotherapy:

- shock method;
- cyclicity;
- intensity;
- a combination of cytostatic drugs.

All chemotherapy drugs are divided into 2 main groups:

Group 1 - chemical agents that specifically affect the cell cycle (cycle-specific) in one or more phases of mitosis.

The 2nd group is chemicals, the action of which is manifested regardless of the cycle (non-cycle specific).

The first stage of cytostatic therapy is the induction of remission (Tables 1–3).

The best effect - cure (or complete remission) - in 80% of cases can be observed with therapy with cytosine arabinazid (100 mg / m²) in combination with daunorubicin (45 mg / m²) for 3 consecutive days, followed by a transition to conventional complexes.

The next stage of treatment is the consolidation of remissions, when in the case of a decrease in the number of blast cells during bone marrow trepanobiopsy, it is necessary to consolidate remission with a more complete eradication (elimination) of leukemia cells and a restraining effect on the "dormant" leukemic subpopulation.

The third stage - the prevention of neuroleukemia - is carried out in patients with both acute lymphoblastic leukemia and acute myeloid leukemia.

The fourth stage is treatment during remission with a maintenance dose of cytostatics. For example, cytosine arabinazid - 30 mg per week or 5-day courses with an interval of 25 days, thioguanine - 40 mg / m².

Forecast. The prognosis for acute leukemia largely depends on the age of the patient and the correct choice of therapy tactics. In patients with acute lymphoblastic leukemia remission for a period of 5-10 years is achieved in 100% of cases, recovery - in 90% of cases. In patients with acute myeloid leukemia under the age of 30, remission in 95% of cases, recovery in 20% of cases.

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